

Spectro-electrochemical X-ray in situ transmission cell for long-term battery cycling

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Abstract

We present a spectro-electrochemical in situ cell for hard X-ray experiments. The cell contains beryllium X-ray windows and allows for scattering and absorption experiments in the transmission geometry. Sealing with three concentric O-rings proves sufficient for long-term battery cycling. The cell was tested with LiMn_2O_4 electrodes. Preliminary X-ray absorption and scattering data are shown as well.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Structural changes in battery electrodes as a result of repeated charging and discharging are often obvious just from visual inspection after disassembling the battery cell. The next step in the characterization of battery electrodes is to apply analytical techniques like chemical titration, X-ray diffraction or electron microscopy on the cycled and on the uncycled electrodes.

An elegant and more efficient way to characterize the electrode during charging and discharging (cycling) with X-rays is to make the battery cell transparent for X-rays by using thin wall material as an X-ray window. The battery can be brought to a particular state of charge or to a particular electrochemical potential by using a potentiostat, while probed with X-rays.

In the last 20 years, numerous in situ battery cells for characterization with X-rays have been developed, mostly for X-ray diffraction and X-ray absorption. Some battery electrode materials are very prone to corrosion in the ambient atmosphere, hence the sealing of the cells plays a very important role. This holds in particular for the alkaline metal-based systems such as lithium batteries. When exposed to the ambient atmosphere, the lithium reacts with the nitrogen in the air to form lithium nitride or, with the humidity to form lithium hydroxide. Some of the electrolytes used in batteries may also form aggressive reaction products; for instance, LiPF_6 forms hydrofluoric acid when in contact with the ambient humidity. Battery charging and discharging is a diffusion limited process, and one charge/discharge cycle may take several hours. Since the structure of electrodes may be dependent upon the number of charge and discharge cycles, experiments often take as long as weeks or months.

Long term in situ experiments that expand over several days or even weeks are difficult because very good sealing is required. Ronci et al. have overcome many of the obstacles related to electrochemical in situ X-ray experiments by switching to energy dispersive X-ray diffraction at very high X-ray energies [1]; Richard et al. used in situ cells that were manufactured in an industrial plant [2], and Gérard's experiments depended on a particular diffractometer type [3]. Koetschau et al. built an in situ cell that allowed for long term experiments, but did not contain lithium metal counter electrodes [4]. Many in situ experiments were performed by the McBreen group in Brookhaven National Laboratory,

in particular in situ X-ray diffraction and absorption, but they measured the cathode of a high-rate industrial battery which could be studied in a short time [5].

In the present paper, we present a handy and re-usable cell with beryllium X-ray windows and sealing rings. It allows charging and discharging for several days without noticeable traces of corrosion of the lithium metal. The cell design allows for X-ray transmission experiments at any hard X-ray source. In particular, the cell was tested at beamline 12-ID [6] at BESSRC-CAT, Advanced Photon Source, Argonne, IL, and at beamlines 2-1 (Figure 1) and 2-3 at Stanford Synchrotron Radiation Laboratory, Menlo Park, CA.

II. TECHNICAL CELL DESIGN

A schematic sketch of the flat cylindrical cell design is shown in Figure 2.

The main support of the cell is a stainless steel disk (15 cm diameter) and a polypropylene (PP) disk (9 cm diameter), both of 5 mm thickness. Both disks are held together by steel bolts (M 5 size) and contain the electrode sample, an ion-conducting separator, the electrolyte and a lithium metal counter electrode. Sealing of the cell is necessary to prevent the electrolyte from drying out and to prevent the sample from chemical reactions with the ambient atmosphere. Our systematic studies showed that three BUNA O-rings are necessary and sufficient to perform the required sealing.

The zone between the steel disk and the PP disk is the sample compartment, which is sealed by three concentric BUNA O-rings with different diameters. Corresponding O-ring grooves are provided in both disks. The right side of the panel displays a magnified view of the portion of the cell that contains the electrode assembly. Both disks have a port of 1 mm \times 2.5 mm in their center to allow the X-ray beam to pass through the cell. The ports on either side of the cell are capped with a Beryllium disk of 380 micrometer thickness (Brush Wellman Company). The Be foils are covered with 25 micron thick Kapton tape to prevent contact with the corrosive electrolyte. The interfaces between the Beryllium disks and the steel disk and the PP disk, respectively, are also sealed with three small concentric BUNA O-rings. On either side, a 30 mm diameter Aluminium disk holds the Beryllium disks in place. In their center, the aluminium disks have a 7 mm diameter hole to allow the X-ray beam to pass through.

The thicknesses of the disks and the width of the holes determine the aspect ratio which

is necessary to cover a desired Q -range for wide-angle X-ray diffraction. In the present case, a 2Θ -angle of about 45° at maximum was permitted which allowed resolution of the [111] Bragg reflection of LiMn_2O_4 at X-ray energies of around 6500 eV. Higher indexed reflexes can be accessed by either adjusting the aspect ratio, or by increasing the X-ray energy. In the latter case the diffractogram will become compressed towards lower Q -values.

Figure 3 shows the disassembled cell after cycling. The left part is the PP plate with one O-ring, the wet separator and the lithium foil underneath. The PP disk has two feed-throughs for stainless steel bolts which serve as contacts to the lithium counter electrode and an optional reference electrode. Each of the two steel bolts is sealed with a tiny O-ring of 2 mm in diameter; these seals are the least reliable parts in terms of contamination from the ambient atmosphere. After several days of operation, the side of the lithium foil next to the steel bolts exhibits typical traces of black lithium nitride, which is an indication that nitrogen from ambient air has diffused around the O-ring. However, this effect was confined to an uncritical area of the cell.

The stainless steel counterpart to the right shows the two other O-rings and the black lithium manganese oxide (working) electrode. Numerous drilled holes in the metal disk allow for versatile mounting of the cell at the X-ray sources (Figure1). The working electrode is in direct contact with the steel disk to provide good electrical contact.

III. EXPERIMENTAL

LiMn_2O_4 powder was synthesized by mixing lithium carbonate Li_2CO_3 and manganese oxide MnO_2 (CMD IC#5, Japan Metals and Chemical) in the stoichiometric amounts and heating it in a muffle furnace with air at 1123 K and subsequent cooling. The manganese oxide was mixed with carbon (graphite from Timcal, and Shawinigan carbon black) and polymer binder (all together 5 wt. %) and cast on an aluminium foil of 25 micron thickness, and subsequently sintered at 423 K, resulting in a positive electrode with 40 micron thickness and 95 wt. % loading of manganese oxide. Electrodes with 25 mm diameter were punched from the foil sheet and vacuum dried for 24 hours, and then stored under Ar gas. The positive electrode, with a polypropylene separator, electrolyte (LiPF_6 dissolved in dimethyl carbonate), and lithium foil (125 micron) as counter electrode, was assembled to form the cell [6]. The battery cell was assembled as follows:

All necessary cell parts, chemicals and tools for assembly were transferred to a helium filled glove bag (Instruments for Research and Industry I²R Inc., Cheltenham PA 19012, USA) for assembly at the synchrotron. The Be windows are already assembled, and the O-rings already placed in the grooves. Lithium foil, as large as the spinel electrode, is punched out from fresh supplies and squeezed on the steel contact bolt of the PP disk; this makes the counter electrode. Next, a single spinel/alu-foil electrode is placed in the center of the steel disk, with the spinel side facing up, and the separator on top of it. A small lithium foil strip is placed on the separator such that it will later match the position of the reference electrode steel bolt on the PP disk. A second piece of separator prevents contact between the reference electrode and counter electrode. Then, some drops of electrolyte are dropped with a pipette on the separator until separator and electrode underneath are fully soaked. Finally, the PP disk is put on top of the steel disk, with all necessary battery cell parts in between, and tightened with bolts. Cell assembly takes a few minutes only.

X-ray diffraction and XANES was performed at BL 2-1 at SSRL (Figure 1), EXAFS at BL 2-3. Small angle X-ray scattering was done at the APS, BEESRC-Cat BL 12-ID [7]. All data were recorded in transmission mode. Detectors were gas ionization chambers for the incident X-ray intensity I_o and the transmitted intensity I_t . A manganese metal foil was used for energy calibration. Only for the SAXS experiment, a CCD camera was used to record the scattered intensity.

IV. RESULTS

A. X-ray diffraction

Figures 4 and 5 display the [111] Bragg reflection of the $\text{Li}_{1+x}\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_4$ spinel lattice at four different X-ray energies (6500, 6533, 6538, 6543 eV). The diffractograms in Figure 4 were recorded at a cell potential of 2.97 eV. This is the "open" cell, disconnected from the potentiostat, and the electrode still being LiMn_2O_4 . During discharging, the [111] reflection splits into two peaks at Q -values of about 1.37 and 1.39 \AA^{-1} , as shown in Figure 5, indicating a cubic \rightarrow tetragonal phase transition. A similar transition like this one is known as the Verwey transition upon temperature changes near room temperature and supposedly caused by the Jahn-Teller effect [10, 11]. We notice that the diffractogram of the open cell already

shows a slight densification of diffracted intensity at $Q=1.38 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, indicating that the spinel as prepared is not entirely a pure cubic phase. The presence of two phases may be due to fact that LiMn_2O_4 undergoes a phase transition from cubic to tetragonal at about 300 K, and our experiments were carried out at room temperature. The critical balance of parameters that affect phase changes and phase purity in lithium manganese oxides is a topic that receives currently much attention from many research groups [12, 13].

B. X-ray absorption near-edge structure spectroscopy

The average oxidation state of manganese in LiMn_2O_4 is 3.5, formally written as $\text{Mn}[3+]\text{Mn}[4+]$. Loading the spinel host with additional lithium ions will cause a net reduction of the manganese. for $\text{Li}_2\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_4$, the average oxidation number of the manganese is $\text{Mn}[3+]$. We have deeply discharged the cell by lithiation so that the manganese became reduced from 3.5 to 2.0. Figure 6 shows the XANES spectra of the cell with open circuit before discharging (dry cell) and the spectrum of the cell at deep discharge with 2.0 average oxidation number. The chemical shift of the spectrum towards lower energies due to reduction is obvious. For reference of the 2.0 state we have plotted the XANES of a rhodochrosite mineral (manganese carbonate MnCO_3) sample as well.

Figure 7 displays the evolution of electric charge in the cell during discharge (lithiation). This curve was obtained by integration of the current through the cell over discharge time, which was monitored with a portable potentiostat from Pine Instruments [6]. The cell was discharged for approximately 27 hours at currents not exceeding 0.2 mA.

By electrochemical lithiation, the stoichiometry changes from LiMn_2O_4 to $\text{Li}_{1+x}\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_4$ with $x \geq 1$, and, consequently, manganese is reduced from an average of 3.5 towards 3.0, or even lower. For $x = 2$, the average oxidation state of manganese in $\text{Li}_{1+x}\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_4$ matches 3.0. The corresponding XANES, not shown here, was recorded approximately 900 minutes after begin of discharging, indicated with letter "A" in Figure 7. The charge accumulated in the cell at this time was around 144 mA min . With 12 mg of spinel in the electrode, the total capacity is calculated to 200 mAh/g . Compared with the theoretical capacity of 148 mAh/g , this result is satisfactory, because parasitic electrochemical side reactions always take place, adding to the overall capacity.

We continued to lithiate the cell for another 730 minutes. At this stage (indicated with

letter "B" in Figure 7 the cell potential was 1.23 V and the total accumulated charge was 3.1 mAh, which amounts to a fictitious discharge capacity of 258.3 mAh/g. The corresponding XANES shows the smallest chemical shift so far among the three spectra. We assign it the oxidation state of Mn⁺² because it matches both literature data of a mineral with Mn⁺² (Rhodochrosite MnCO₃, [8]) as well as the extrapolated calibration curve of the chemical shift for manganese compounds [8]. The XANES spectrum of Rhodochrosite as obtained by Shiraishi et al. is included in Figure 6 as a reference [9].

C. EXAFS

EXAFS spectra were recorded at beamline 2.3 at SSRL during discharge/lithiation of the cell. Figure 8 shows the absorption curves recorded when the average Mn oxidation state was 3.5 and 3.0, respectively. These EXAFS data were analyzed with the computer program *EXAFSPAK* [14]. The evolution of the Fourier Transform (FT) amplitudes of 3 scans during the entire discharge process is displayed in Figure 9. In both scans, we assigned the manganese oxidation states, derived from the chemical shift of the XANES spectra. The deepest state of discharge obtained in this particular experiment corresponds to an average manganese oxidation state of +3.09, and to a nominal stoichiometry Li_{1.82}Mn₂O₄. These data have not been corrected for the phase shift, hence are given in terms of $R+\Delta R$. The peaks at 1.92 Å and 2.82 Å correspond to the Mn-O and Mn-Mn distances, respectively.

We notice that, upon discharging, the intensity of the peaks decreases systematically. The reverse effect - increasing peak heights upon charging - has already been reported [8, 15] and was attributed to structural ordering of Mn-O₆ octahedra when manganese approaches a uniform valence state of Mn⁺⁴. The extension of this interpretation for the discharge process is obviously not applicable. This is not surprising because the manganese is being reduced during discharge from an average oxidation state of Mn^{+3.5} towards Mn^{+3.0}, and Mn⁺³ is known to be the high-spin Jahn-Teller ion of manganese with a pronounced tetragonal distortion of either Mn-O₆ octahedra.

D. ASAXS

ASAXS is small angle scattering with at least two different X-ray energies. Scattering curves (SC) are obtained with an X-ray energy before the absorption edge of a particular element, and right after the absorption edge. This technique is called contrast variation and allows to separate the scattering contribution from objects containing a particular chemical component from other contributions [16].

Battery electrodes are relatively complex in terms of microstructure and chemical composition. They contain carbon, active material such as the spinel, and also pores and electrolyte. The X-ray scattering curve obtained by an in situ experiment contains structural information of the electrode, but also of the cell parts.

With SAXS at one single X-ray energy only, no unambiguous distinction can be made between either phases. Tuning the X-ray energy to the manganese K-edge however, and subtracting the SC taken before the absorption edge of manganese from the SC taken at the absorption edge, yields an SC which contains information about the manganese rich structures only.

Anomalous small angle X-ray scattering (ASAXS) was carried out at the Advanced Photon Source (APS, BESSRC-CAT) for a period of 40 hours, during which the cell was slowly charged to 4.3 Volt, and thereafter discharged back to 3.05 Volt.

Scattering curves were sequentially recorded at X-ray energies between 6350 and 6550 eV near the manganese K-shell absorption edge to allow for anomalous scattering of the Mn atoms and thus for contrast variation. Due to the thin design of the in situ cell with beryllium X-ray windows, a single scattering curve could be acquired in only 0.1 seconds. Therefore the ASAXS studies can be considered a time resolved experiment. About 60 sets of such each 20 SC were recorded during the entire experiment. The SC at energies 6400 eV and 6545 eV were chosen for further data analysis [6].

Figure 10 displays scattering curves of the entire cell, obtained at two different X-ray energies after charging and subsequent discharging of the electrode in the cell. The corresponding energies are noted accordingly in the plot. Intensity changes among either four SC as functions of the X-ray energy are due to X-ray fluorescence and anomalous scattering of the manganese. By appropriate subtraction algorithms [6, 16], the scattering of the Mn-containing objects can be obtained.

This curve was analyzed for anomalous scattering as described in [16] and fitted with two Guinier functions [6]:

$$I \propto \exp(-Q^2 R_g^2/3) \quad (1)$$

Since scattering contributions from the cell parts, carbon, and pores, are subtracted, the lower SC in Figure 10 represents structural data of the Mn in the electrode only.

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FIG. 1: In situ cell mounted to the X-ray diffractometer at BL 2-1, SSRL. Cables for three electrodes are connected as well.

FIG. 2: Cross sectional overview of the central parts of the in situ cell. Not all of the parts refer to the same scale.

FIG. 3: Disassembled cell after use. Left: PP disk with one O-ring and metal lithium under still wet separator. Right: Steel disk with two O-rings and lithium manganese oxide electrode. Ruler shows size in inches.

FIG. 4: [111] Bragg reflection for 4 different X-ray energies, recorded when cell potential was 2.97 eV, the electrode still being LiMn_2O_4 .

FIG. 5: Bragg reflections of the original [111] peak for 4 different X-ray energies, recorded when cell potential was 1.54 eV. Splitted peaks indicate phase transition from cubic to tetragonal.

FIG. 6: XANES spectra of the LiMn_2O_4 at open cell, and at 1.54 Volt deep discharge. XANES spectrum of Rhodochrosite after [8] is plotted for reference (reproduced from [8] by using Quick-Trace [9]).

FIG. 7: Evolution of the charge in the cell with increasing charging time (obtained from integration of current through discharge process).

FIG. 8: X-ray absorption spectra for EXAFS purposes for LiMn_2O_4 and $\text{Li}_2\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_4$ (later refers to point A in Figure 9).

FIG. 9: Fourier magnitude for EXAFS data from the cell at three different valence states for the manganese: 3.50, 3.22, and 3.09

FIG. 10: Two scattering curves of the entire in situ cell at 2 different X-ray energies: 6400 (dotted) and 6545 eV (solid). Scattering curve in center is the weighted difference $1.365 \cdot I(6400\text{eV}) - I(6545\text{eV})$. Scattering curve at bottom includes Q^{-4} -subtraction after Porod. Solid line is from two combined Guinier fits.